

THE SOCIAL AND MULTIFUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES OF SLANG IN MODERN ENGLISH

Makhsudbek Nurmatov

*Master's student on Linguistic (English),
Uzbekistan State World Language University*

Abstract: *The article is concerned with study slang in Modern English. Specifically, it provides several definition of slang suggested by prominent scholars such as Carl Sandburg, Michael Swan. The article also focuses on the cases when the slang can be used and informs on social features of the slang.*

Key words: *Colloquial words, informal speech, non-standard language, secret language, societies, social group, vocabulary.*

Аннотация: *Мақолада замонавий инглиз тилидаги жаргонларни ўрганиш билан боғлиқ масалага тўхталинган. Хусусан, унда Карл Сандбург, Майкл Свон каби таниқли олимлар томонидан таклиф қилинган жаргоннинг бир нечта таърифлари келтириб ўтилади. Таҳлиллар орқали жаргондан фойдаланиш мумкин бўлган ҳолатларга ҳам эътибор қаратилган ва жаргоннинг ижтимоий хусусиятлари ҳақида маълумот берилган.*

Калим сўзлар: *Сўзлашув тили, норасмий нутқ, ностандарт тил, яширин тил, ижтимоий гуруҳ, лугат.*

Аннотация: *Статья посвящена изучению сленга в современном английском языке. В частности, в нем дается несколько определений сленга, предложенных видными учеными, такими как Карл Сандберг, Майкл Свон. В статье также акцентируется внимание на случаях употребления сленга и сообщается о социальных особенностях сленга.*

Ключевые слова: *Разговорные слова, неформальная речь нестандартный язык, тайный язык общества, социальная группа, словарь.*

Slang is an integral part of the English vocabulary and in recent times, it has crept into everyday English language. According to the Webster's "Third New International Dictionary" slang is regarded as a non-standard vocabulary composed of words and senses characterized primarily by connotations of extreme informality and usually a currency not limited to a particular region and composed typically of coinages or arbitrarily changed words, clipped or shortened forms, extravagant, forced or facetious figures of speech, or verbal novelties usually experiencing quick popularity and relatively rapid decline into disuse.

The American poet Carl Sandburg defines slang as the language "which takes off its coat, spits on its hands and goes to work". Slang has also been characterized as "an ever-changing set of colloquial words and phrases generally considered distinct from and socially lower than the standard language. It occurs in all languages, and the existence of this part of the vocabulary is probably as old as the language itself". [4,14] Swan states that slang is a word, expression or special use of language found mainly in very informal speech, often in the usage of particular groups of people. [8,24]

In general, all linguists agree that slang is nonstandard vocabulary composed of words or senses characterized primarily by connotations of extreme informality and usually by a currency not limited to a particular region. It is composed typically of coinages or arbitrarily changed words, clipped or shortened forms, extravagant, forced, or facetious figures of speech, or verbal novelties. They are identified and distinguished by contrasting them to standard literary vocabulary. [1,249]

One of the important aspects to consider when discussing slang is the different situations where we are most likely and most unlikely to use slang. Slang is used by all kinds of groups of people who share situations or interests. The group which uses these words is always in minority, and often uses slang to set its members apart or make it difficult for ordinary people to understand them. According to Andersson & Trudgill, people use a lot more slang when speaking than when writing. [2,72] However, in novels, many authors are likely to

use slang, especially in dialogues as this is a good way of showing what the characters are like. Consider the following example, *Well now, I be ding-busted*. This is a line from *The adventures of Huckleberry Finn* where the run-away black man Jim is talking to Huck saying “*well now, I’ll be damned*”. By consciously writing in this way, Twain gives life to the character Jim as a poorly educated slave using a far less formal language than other characters in the book. [2, 72] In other forms of written media one is more likely to see slang in tabloids than in broadsheets, and perhaps there is a connection with the fact that broadsheets are considered to contain more legitimate news whereas more gossip-like news are found in tabloids?

People who are admired will often be copied by others so a lot of the slang used is spread via, for instance, the film or music industry. Others who are likely to be influential when it comes to slang usage are comedians, talk-show hosts, politicians and sport-stars. TV-shows that become very popular and are aired for many years are most likely to influence their audience, such as *Seinfeld*. [3, 8]

There are many reasons people use slang words and expressions. It can be used just for fun or as a way to be witty or clever. You can use it to be different or startling. Even if you don’t know it, slang enriches the language. Many use it as a way to be friendly, or to show that they belong to a certain group or profession. Some engage in slang usage to be secretive, like those in secret societies, children, students, or prisoners.

Most people use slang because they are individuals who desire uniqueness, it stands to reason that slang has been in existence for as long as language has been in existence. Even so, the question of why slang develops within a language has been hotly debated. Most agree that the question is still unanswered, or perhaps it has many answers. Regardless, there is no doubt that we can better explain slang's existence by analyzing how and why it exists.

The *Historical Dictionary of American Slang* points out that many groups "use slang largely because they lack political power." It is simply a safe and effective way that people rebel against the establishment. Often, however, it

appears that slang is ever present and exists even in complacent times. It is created by individuals and perpetuated based upon its usefulness and applicability.

Others, however, condemn the use of slang, believing that it undermines the standard language and reflects poorly upon its users. Parshall notes that Ambrose Bierce, in his dictionary, called slang "the grunt of the human hog." Even The Oxford English Dictionary's 1989 edition defines slang as "the special vocabulary used by any set of persons of a low or disreputable character; language of a low and vulgar type." In fact, both Crystal and The Historical Dictionary of American Slang point out that Samuel Johnson and Jonathan Swift produced the very first dictionaries partly out of great concern for the corruption of the standard English language.

Whatever the reason(s), slang is here to stay, and its longevity demands attention and explication. "According to the British lexicographer, Eric Partridge, people use slang for any of at least 15 reasons:

1. In sheer high spirits, by the young in heart as well as by the young in years; 'just for the fun of the thing'; in playfulness or waggishness.
2. As an exercise either in wit and ingenuity or in humour. (The motive behind this is usually self-display or snobbishness, emulation or responsiveness, delight in virtuosity).
3. To be 'different', to be novel.
4. To be picturesque (either positively or - as in the wish to avoid insipidity - negatively).
5. To be unmistakably arresting, even startling.
6. To escape from clichés, or to be brief and concise. (Actuated by impatience with existing terms.)
7. To enrich the language. (This deliberateness is rare save among the well-educated, Cockneys forming the most notable exception; it is literary rather than spontaneous.)
8. To lend an air of solidity, concreteness, to the abstract; of earthiness to the idealistic; of immediacy and appositeness to the remote. (In the cultured the effort

is usually premeditated, while in the uncultured it is almost always unconscious when it is not rather subconscious.)

9. To lessen the sting of, or on the other hand to give additional point to, a refusal, a rejection, a recantation;

10. To speak or write down to an inferior, or to amuse a superior public; or merely to be on a colloquial level with either one's audience or one's subject matter.

11. For ease of social intercourse. (Not to be confused or merged with the preceding.)

12. To induce either friendliness or intimacy of a deep or a durable kind. (Same remark.)

13. To show that one belongs to a certain school, trade, or profession, artistic or intellectual set, or social class; in brief, to be 'in the swim' or to establish contact.

14. Hence, to show or prove that someone is not 'in the swim'.

15. To be secret - not understood by those around one. (Children, students, lovers, members of political secret societies, and criminals in or out of prison, innocent persons in prison, are the chief exponents.)

References

1. Arnold I.V. Lexicology of modern English. Moscow: Высшая школа, 1986.- 295 с.
2. Andersson, Lars-Gunnar & Trudgill, Peter. Bad Language. London: Penguin, 1990-72 p
3. Battistella, Edwin L. Bad Language: Are Some Words Better than Others? Oxford: Oxford University press, 2005-8 p
4. Dickson P. Slang! – New York : Pocket Books, 1990-674 p
5. Eble, C. Slang and Sociability. In-group language among college students. London and Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 1996-333 p
6. Mattiello. E An Introduction to English Slang. Milano, Italy; Polimetrica 2008-324 p
7. Pavlova N.V. Slang as a part of the English language.// English.-2003,-N32
8. Swan, Michael. Practical English Usage. Oxford University Press. 2005-658 p